

HARMONY AND HEALING: MUSIC'S ROLE IN 21ST CENTURY GLOBAL RECONCILIATION

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Abstract: In this 21st Century, Global disintegrations abound. Conflicts *Century* initiated by nationalistic, ethnic, religious or communalist elites who *reformation, Music*, exacerbate and reinforce 'identity' difference, grievances and aspirations for *Agent, Global* their own ends. How to tackle them in order to achieve lasting peace and *reconciliation* reconciliation should be a focus of every nation. Music is a phenomenon that cut across the sphere in realization of numerous prerequisite of the society. As a medium for self-actualization of the societal needs in respect of universal, national, ethnic or religious differences, it contributes to the integration, unanimity and harmony. Through music, conservation of laws and order are renowned and exposed publicly. Music is educative, entertaining and an intricate part of the development of the mind, body and soul. Attempt is made in this paper to unveil the relevance of music in achieving global reconciliation in this 21st century and it was discovered that music plays an important role in preventing conflicts, promoting conflict resolution and sustaining peace. Music with properly structured contexts permeates the innermost being and project peace and understanding among nations. It is hoped that this paper would open people's minds and souls to see that through music, people are introduced to truths necessary for understanding and correcting the ills of the world and societies by which peace and reconciliation can be achieved. This descriptive survey employed musicological tools such as review of related literature and discography.

Keywords: Music, Reconciliation, Conflict Resolution, Peacebuilding, Identity

INTRODUCTION

Reconciliation is a word or concept resulting to creating an understanding for peace (universal, national, ethnic, or cultural diversities). The desire of many people in a condensation of conflict is to create peace. In the steam of crisis, resolution to it requires not just restoring damaged infrastructure and paying compensations, but also working with peoples' minds, bringing peace building activities down from the conference tables into the field on the level of local communities and to the people directly affected by violent conflict. The central intent of conflict resolution and reconciliation is to create a positive peace and security that translates into a stable, social equilibrium in which the reoccurrence of fresh disputes does not escalate and degenerate into armed conflict (Azakar, 2003).

Working with peoples' mind to bringing lasting peace is done through communication, meaning, verbal and non-verbal symbols and exchange of ideas or transaction of information from sender to a receiver. Communication is viewed as a situation in which a communicator manipulates information to bring

about changes in an audience to be motivated by a conviction that the audience will accept the information and behave accordingly.

Among many communication tools with which communicators communicate, music use to make an impact on the society. As pointed out by Okafor (2005) “music is about human feelings and every human art is ultimately human” (p. 1). Music has certain qualities and elements that cut across cultures and create a powerful and effective medium for intercultural communication. Music has several functions as recognized by Merriam (1964) among which is “contribution to the integration of society”. Music whose context is properly structured projects peace and understanding among nations. Music of peace are propagated through international festivals, competitions, ICT gadgets (internet, Radio, TV, CDs, DVD) Unions and NGOs.

INTEGRATION:

Integration according to Okafor (2006) is “a process when social engineers, development planners, stake-men and social entrepreneurs begin to think of bringing many societies within their society into one” (p. 131). It is a method used to sum the effects of a continuously varying quantity or function by treating it as a very large number of infinitely small. It is the process of integrating fixing parts together to form a whole, mixing people or causing people to mix freely with other groups in society. One of the objectives of integration is often the desire to have a common focus among the very many people of many cultural groups in the societies. Another reason for desiring the integration of society according to Okafor (2006) is the achievement of peace, harmony and fraternity.

Integration is often introduced as the reverse process to differentiation. In this situation, the differentiation initiated by nationalistic, ethnic and religious elites who aggravate and reinforce identity difference, grievances and aspiration for their own ends. Nationalistic is characterized by nationalism-an extreme pride in the history, cultural loyalty to one’s nation’s patriotism especially as above loyalty to other groups or to individual interests, devotion to the interest or culture of one’s nation. The belief that nations will benefit from acting independently rather than collectively, emphasizing national rather than international goals. This is considered a major contributing cause of World War 1, World war11, and many other wars of the modern era.

Ethnic Conflict is one of the internationally recognized major social conflicts. Its nature varies substantially ranging from peaceful expression of grievances to outright use of physical force or violence. Ethnic conflict varies from peaceful reflection of conflict of interests to a violent struggle and civil wars. Okafor (2006) pointed out that “gaps or divisions are often caused by factors like ethnicity because in a tribe or ethnic group, a people feels a common identity and a common need to provide security against hostile forces” (p. 129), culture, religion, economic opportunity, poverty and education which was primarily meant to be a unifying cause where everybody has the same opportunity to develop the mind by being educated. This will make the society to be more positively propelled towards development and towards integration. . Religion is another factor that causes global disintegration. Members of religious groups have common beliefs and attitudes and these may influence their willingness to work closely with people of other religions. Some religions impose patterns of behavior

which may affect other religions. For instance, Boko Haram (western education is forbidden), a militant Islamic movement based in northeast Nigeria. This group was founded by Mohammed Yusuf in 2002 in Maiduguri, the capital of the north. The group received training and funds from Al-Qaeda in Islamic Maghreb, and was designated by the US as a terrorist organization in November 2013. They are committed to the prophet's Teachings for propagation and jihad. Okafor (2006) supported this when he noted:

Another factor which causes division in the society and in many cultures is religion. Though, all the religions in the world have some very noble commonalities. Religion by its very nature often tends to be ethnocentric because each religion thinks of itself as the last word of the supreme power, in other words, the best, the way, the life, the truth. Because of that, there is often the need to let each religion thrive while all of them have a sort of concord or coexistence (p. 130).

In the mist of all these disintegrations, there is need for global reconciliation for lasting peace to be achieved. All efforts should be done globally. According to Derefaka (2004), globalization is defined as "the intensification of worldwide social relations which link distant localities in such a way that local happenings are shaped by events occurring many miles away" (p. 45). Efurhieve (2012), sees globalization as "the application of science and technology made possible for information to be gathered, processed, used and delivered in our globalized environment" (p.28). Idolor (2005) glimpses globalization as "the interconnectivity of people, irrespective of distance, race and regional boundaries" (p. 81). Soola (2003) sees it as "that which seeks to universalize the culture and economics of the globe through technology and telecommunication, as well as to ensure an unhindered inflow of information, goods and services" (p.10). Globalization as a universal practices (phenomena must create opportunities for conflict reconciliation to achieve lasting peace.

MUSIC AND CONFLICT RESOLUTION

Music is the art of arranging tones in a systematic sequence so as to create a unified and unremitting composition. In veracity, music does not have any one concrete meaning. It has different meanings for different people. In view of this, Okafor (2004) rightly puts it "there is hardly a universally satisfactory and acceptable definition of music. This is because music, deals with emotions and consequently affects not only individuals but even groups and sub-groups of people differently" (p. 147).

As a humanly organized sound, people compose music to achieve certain emotional ends. Vidal (2012) pointed out that "throughout history, music has been one of the most common form by which man expresses his emotions, feelings and sentiments" (p. 55). Music is an art form whose medium is sound and silence. Its common elements are pitch (which governs melody and harmony), rhythm (and its associates concepts tempo, meter and articulation, dynamics and qualities of music and texture. Music is a source of inspiration and expression. It is a way to express and release emotions. It can carry a message that is relative to real life situations. In relation to this, Okafor (2005) pointed out that:

Only sounds which have been deliberately organized by man to specific ends for expression of emotion, communication of ideas, touching the sense and emotions, calming the nerves or tuning the minds to certain planes of communication and worship, qualified to be called

music (p. 1) There are different types of music which can generally be grouped into three categories, namely; vocal, instrumental and dance. Dance music is designed for body expression. It always involves the voice, instruments and costumes. Instrumental music is the type of music that does not engross singing, or rather music which utilizes singing, but does not feature it prominently. Vocal music is a genre of music performed by one or more singers. It involves singing of songs, anthems, and so on. Vocal music is performed with instrumental accompaniment. When performed without instrumental accompaniment, it is called a cappella. In vocal music, singing provides the main focus of the piece. Vocal music typically features sung words called lyrics or song text which usually carries the message of the song.

Music with good or well-structured texts permeates the innermost being and project peace and understanding among nations. Music plays an important role in preventing conflicts, promoting conflict resolution and sustaining peace. As an agent of global reconciliation, music works on the mind of people. It finds their way into the inner places of the soul, making a very powerful effect on them. Music is very useful in preventing conflict. Conflict prevention refers to a variety of activities aimed at anticipating and averting the outbreak of conflict. It is any structural means to keep international tension and disputes from escalating into significant violence and use of armed forces.

Preventive measures are designed to resolve, contain and manage, so that conflicts do not crystallize. In this situation, the music of nonviolent are made using the music of nonviolent actions. Music and musicians often emerge at both the center and periphery of non violent movements providing a megaphone for demands and a platform for expressing grievances and preserving collective identities. NGOs and humanitarian organizations play an integral and increasingly important role in conflict prevention, owing to their knowledge of and involvement in potential conflict areas. There is however an uneasy relationship between humanitarian organizations and other parties engaged in conflict prevention and peace implementation. . Music whose context is properly structured projects peace and understanding among nations. For instance, an international NGO named UNPOLAC (United Nations Positive Life hood Award Centre) projects peace through music which they recorded and propagated through Radios, TV etc. The music is titled “**Peace**”.

IGBO	ENGLISH
<p><i>Udo amaka nwanne m</i> <i>Udo bu idi n'otu nke umunne</i> <i>Udo bu inyere mmadu ibe gi aka, ka onwee</i> <i>oganihu, ghara inwere gi anya ufu – udo</i> <i>amaka – Udo na-ewepu onuma, o na-eweta</i> <i>anuri</i> <i>Udo na-edozi obodo</i> <i>O na-eweta anuri</i> <i>Udo na-ehicha anya mmiri ne-eme ka</i> <i>ihunanya too ato</i> <i>Ezi udo na-esite n'aka Chineke abia</i> <i>Lezie anya mee ka udo di n'ebe obula ino,</i> <i>N'ih na udo di mkpa n'elu uwa.</i></p>	<p>My brother, peace is so good Peace is unification of relations Peace is helping someone to progress So that he will not envy you, Peace is so good Peace removes anger, it brings joy Peace reforms community Peace brings joy Peace wipes away tears and sustains love Everlasting peace comes from God Look around and make sure peace is where ever you are Because peace is so important in the world.</p>

UDOAMAKA

NWOBU S.

U - do u-do u-do a-ma ka nwa-nem u - do a-ma - ka nwa-nem u-do bi -
8 di n' otu nke u - nu me u-do bu i - nye-re ma-dui - be gia - ka ko-nwco - ko-nwco-
16 ga-ni - hu gha-rai - nwe-re gia-nyu - fu u-do a-ma - ka - - - u-do ne - we puo-nu-ma
24 o - nae - we - ta - nu - ri u - do u - do o - ne - do-zi-o-bo-do u - do u - do
32 o - ne - we - ta - nu - ri u-do ne - hi-cha-nya mi - ri na c - me ki - hu - na-nya to - a - too
40 o e - zu - do ne - si-te na - ka chi - ne - ka - bia nye-ziea - ka me-e ku - do
49 di ne - bco - bu - la i noo n'i - hi-nu - do di mkpa n'e - nu - wa

This peaceful music acts as preventive measures to conflicted parties. With this type of music, even the harden hearts must liquefy and cuddle peace and seek for reconciliation. With this music, disintegrated societies must reintegrate.

Music is also very useful in promoting conflict resolution. Conflict resolution or reconciliation is conceptualized as the method and processes involved in facilitating the peaceful ending of conflict and

retribution. Ogege (2009) asserted that “conflict resolution connotes a sense of finality where the parties to a conflict are mutually satisfied with the outcome of a settlement and the conflict is resolved in a true sense” (p. 406). Miller (cited in Ogege 2009:405) sees it as “a variety of approaches aimed at terminating conflicts through the constructive solving of problems, distinct from management of conflict”. This term may also be used interchangeably with dispute resolution where arbitration and litigation processes are critically involved. The concept can be thought to encompass the use of nonviolent resistance measures by conflicted parties in an attempt to promote effective resolution. Music that touches the heart, soul and body makes reconciliation easier. For instance, Augustine Ukwu in his music titled “**Lets Reconcile**” projects peace and reconciliation as best. Through such music, peace is achieved.

IGBO	ENGLISH
<i>Ka anyi dozie na o ka mma, ka anyi dozie na o ka mma</i>	Lets reconcile for that is the best thing to do
<i>Okwu ahu diri mu na gi, ka anyi dozie ya</i>	That conflict we have, lets reconcile

KANYI DOZIE (LETS RECONCILE)

AUGUSTINE UKWU

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

Music also functions in sustenance of peace. It is a vehicle to promote peace and build awareness of the necessity of peace and avoid future conflict. Music is a unifying agent that promotes peace, harmony and co-operation among societies. It stimulates a whole range of emotions and perceptions. Another

prominent role of music is its potential to affect tolerance and reconciliation between hostile peoples. Music can be an amazing bridge between people, transcending all kinds of prejudices. When music pours freely from the heart, people are united in its flow. It has incredible potential and when created with good intention, it can help make the world a better place.

Peace is achieved through music festivals, music films, etc. There are music around the world, being played for global change. For instance, Bob Marley in his song “**One Love**” preached that it is time for the world to unite as a human race. His lyrics- one love, one heart, let’s get together and feel alright projects need to be unified as one. Other songs for peace and reconciliation include “**Redemption song**” by Bob Marley, “**Different colors, one people**” by Lucky Dube etc. Music has influence on human beings and all manner of conflict can be resolved with music.

Peaceful music is the type that is needed to achieve reconciliation. Peaceful type because, in as much as music can help to make the world a more peaceful place, it has a dark side as well. There are songs that celebrate hostilities, viciousness, revulsion and humiliation. Music has the power to heal but it also has the power to impair. Music is peaceful or not peaceful not because of the inherent character of music itself, but because of the way it is used. Some good music is deliberately composed to be unpleasant and to unsettle rather than calm the emotions. It is not good or peaceful when it is hurtful to some people.

STRATEGIES FOR CONFLICT RESOLUTION

Achieving global reconciliation through music in this 21st Century requires certain strategies.

(1) **Celebrations of international festivals.** Music festivals are particularly important in social integration because they deal with themes that may either be current or germane or momentous in the societies or even meant to motivate or mobilize the societies. In this, sharing of music as the glory of the human soul, people often celebrate oneness. Okafor (2006) noted on the importance of music festivals thus:

They address not only new music but also new ideas. They also bring tourists and also a concourse of artists together. When these artists and tourists meet, ideas are exchanged, which go on not to light up the world but also to unite the people to make them feel together as one in the common field of music” (p. 136).

Mbiti (cited in Okafor 2005:13) sees festivals as a means of unification of people when he comments: “through festivals, the life of the community is renewed. People are entertained

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and their tensions find an outlet. Festivals also, bring together the people as a group thus strengthening their unity and cohesion”.

Many festivals are identified as being world music. Such festivals have featured many artists from countries around the world. Examples of such festival include:

(a) The Globe to Globe World Music

Festival which takes place in the city of Kingston, Melbourne, for 2days each year in January.

(b) The Dhaka World Music Festival that takes place in Dhaka.

(c) Sunfest ,an annual 4-day World Music Festival that happens in London.

- (d) OFFest, a five day World Music Festival held every summer in Skopje.
- (e) Rainforest World Music Festival is held in Malaysia.
- (f) Mawazine is a festival of world music that takes place annually in Rabat, Morocco, featuring Arab and international music icons.
- (g) Musicport world music festival held annually at the Spa pavilion, Whitby, North Yorkshire.
- (h) The California World Music Festival is held each July at the Nevada country Fair grounds.
- (i) The World Sacred Music Festival is held annually in Olympic, Washington State. Music festivals unite people together. It unites men and spirits together as one and therefore should be defined as an incorporator of societies. It is the bond and the glory of the human heart and soul.
- (2) **Conducting of different musical activities.** Music as a medium of expression will perform very important role in different musical activities when conducted. Such activity which, besides the direct purposes will promote an establishment of constructive and confidential relationship with the conflicting parties at different levels. Musical activities like choir festivals and music competitions where people of diverse cultures showcase their culture (music) exposing their musical instruments including their compositional techniques. Sports like Olympic Games where different countries that participate in it begin with the rendition of each country's national anthem. People learn the various national anthem and the solemnity and patriotism attached to it which is highly honoured. For example Nigerian Anthem

THE NIGERIAN NATIONAL ANTHEM

BEN. ODIASE 1978

A - - rise O Com-pa - triots. Ni - ge - ria call O - bey: To

Serve our fa - ther Land. With love, and Strength, and faith; The la - bour of our

he - roes past shall ne - ver be in vain; to serve with heart and might. one

na - tion bound in fre - dom, peace and u - ni - ty

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.Oh God of creation, direct our noble cause
Guide our leaders' right
Help our youth the truth to know,
In love and honesty to grow,
And living just and true;
Great lofty heights attain
To build a nation where peace and justice shall reign

Okafor (2006) pointed out that different nations each have their own musical slogans, songs and other musical patterns which are identified with them. He further asserted that: These various musical acts, in addition to expressing identity in specific ways also touch the hearts of the people of various groupings, stir or challenge their patriotism and their ability to dare to win, challenge them to equal or surpass the magnanimity or greatness of their forebears or encode in the soul stirring ways what the people live by (p. 137).

National anthems of various people appeal to them in a way that no other music can. Such music is designed at bringing unity into the diversity as a means of social integration, meant to unite and express the unity of people, all preaching peace, integration and personal commitment and patriotism to various nations. (3) **Music Advert for mobilization.**

The essence of advert is to mobilize people and for world awareness. Peaceful music are propagated or promoted through modern times radio, televisions, satellite, travel, technology (gramophone records, audio and video tape records, CDs, DVDs, Cinema houses) etc. global reconciliation awareness is created and propagated through such means.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, many conflicts arise as a result of breakdown in communication. Therefore in preventing conflict is the importance of ensuring that communication takes place as effectively as possible. Among many communication tools, music use to, make an impact on the society. It allows for expression of ideas when words aren't enough. In this 21st century, music acts as an agent in global reconciliation. Music contributes to the strengthening of a global awareness, to understanding that we are all part of the same planetary family, enabling people to reach deeper levels of mutual respect by enhancing the perception of their common humanity. Music is an agent of global reconciliation that plays an important role in preventing conflicts, promoting conflict resolution and sustaining peace. Since conflict emanates from the mind, music which is the rhythm and harmony that find their way into the inner places of the soul making a very powerful effect on people becomes the antidotes to conflicts. People who play music together and get to know each other in a more intimate way find it easier to promote structures based on solidarity and human care. Structures that will lead to loyalty, to the whole of human kinds and not to any specific nation or other group.

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